

ERC study on repositories

This form is designed to collect data for updating the [Study on the Readiness of Research Data and Literature Repositories to Facilitate compliance with the Open Science Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement \(OS HE MGA\) Requirements](#), which was commissioned to a group of independent experts by the European Research Council Executive Agency (ERCEA).

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

1 Scope

The data collected through this form will be used to update the Inventory of Identified Trusted Repositories that is associated with the [Study](#).

The overall purpose of the study and this update is to provide guidance to ERC grantees and, in general, to HE beneficiaries on how to comply with the OS requirements linked to their grant.

This survey is structured to reflect the methodology of the study. It has been designed to support a two-step assessment, i.e. identifying trusted repositories first, and then collecting information on the metadata structure, adding the other crucial requirements for a repository to be able to facilitate compliance with the OS HE requirements.

The survey sections are designed to collect different types of information:

- In the second section of the survey, general information about the repository is collected;
- the third section is dedicated to obtaining information about elements that can be used to identify the repository as trusted;
- the fourth section inquires about metadata linked to the OS HE requirements;
- additional information about the repository is collected in the fifth section;
- comments can be provided in the last section of the survey.

It is important to highlight that the inventory displays data on a relatively small sample of repositories that were preselected using the methodology explained in the published study.

It should not be considered as an exhaustive list of trusted repositories.

Not having been included in the sample does not automatically mean that the repository would not qualify for being included.

This form will close on 07 January 2024.

Data and an accompanying report are envisaged to be published by June 2024.

1.1 Terms and Conditions

[Survey Participation Terms and Conditions .pdf](#)

2 General information about the repository

In this section, you will be asked to provide information to identify and locate the repository, as well as to categorise it.

You will also be able to provide a valid contact in case further clarifications will be required.

I accept the terms provided in the [Terms and Conditions](#).

*** 2.1 Repository name**

The extended repository name, as it appears in the repository website

2.2 Repository short name or acronym (if available)

*** 2.3 Repository URL**

The URL of your repository

2.4 If you agree to be contacted in case further clarifications of your responses are required, please provide us with a valid email.

*** 2.5** What type(s) of digital objects can be deposited in the repository? Select all that apply.

- Data
- Literature - articles, books, conference proceedings, etc...
- Software/Code
- Other - media, lectures, etc...

*** 2.6** What type of literature does the repository host? Select all that apply.

- Pre-prints (including manuscripts that have been submitted to a venue for peer-reviewed publications but have not yet been accepted for publication in that venue)
- Published / accepted articles (Version of Record or Accepted Author Manuscript)
- Reports, project deliverables or other grey literature
- Books
- Chapters
- Conference proceedings
- Project Proposals
- Other
- All of the above

*** 2.7** You selected "Other" to identify the type of content that can be deposited in the repository. Please specify.

* 2.8 Please specify the eligibility criteria for uploading research results to your repository. Choose the option that best describes your repository:

- Open to All: Researchers from any community or institution, including Horizon Europe ERC grantees, can upload their research results without restrictions.
- Community/Discipline-Specific: Only research results (data or literature) linked to a specific community or discipline can be uploaded to the repository.
- Institution-Specific: Only researchers affiliated with a specific institution (or group of institutions) are allowed to upload their research results.
- Country-Specific: Only researchers affiliated with institutions based in a specific country are allowed to upload their research results.
- Funder-Specific: Only researchers supported by a specific funder, or group of funders, are allowed to upload their research results, regardless of community or institution.
- Other: If there are additional or specific eligibility criteria, please describe them in the space provided.

2.9 You selected "Other" as answer to the previous question. Please specify the specific eligibility criteria to upload results in your repository.

* 2.10 How would you define the access to the repository content?

Note that this question refers to the general content of the repository and not to single access rights for specific records in the repository.

- Users can access the content of the repositories without barriers.
- Users can access the repository contents only after an authentication/authorisation process.
- The content is only available to internal users managing the repository (internal archive).

3 Trusted repository identification

This section is designed to identify trusted repositories using the methodology defined in the study available [here](#).

The Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement and Annotated Model Grant Agreement state that beneficiaries must ensure deposition of and open access to publications (and research data, where the case) through **trusted repositories**.

Trusted repositories can be grouped into three categories, which may overlap:

- certified repositories, such as those certified by international organisations or government-authorised certification bodies (e.g. CoreTrustSeal, nestor Seal DIN31644, ISO16363)
- disciplinary or domain repositories commonly used and endorsed by the research communities, and which are recognised internationally

- general-purpose repositories, institutional repositories or any other repositories that present the essential characteristics of trusted repositories, i.e.:
 - display specific characteristics of organisational, technical and procedural quality, such as services, mechanisms and/or provisions that are intended to secure the integrity and authenticity of their contents, thus facilitating their use and re-use in the short- and long-term. Trusted repositories have specific provisions in place and offer explicit information online about their policies, which define their services (e.g. acquisition, access, security of content, long-term sustainability of service including funding, etc.)
 - provide broad, equitable and ideally open access to content free at the point of use, as appropriate, and respect applicable legal and ethical limitations. They assign persistent unique identifiers to contents (e.g. DOIs, handles, etc.), such that the contents (publications, data and other research outputs) are unequivocally referenced and thus citeable. They ensure that contents are accompanied by metadata sufficiently detailed and of sufficiently high quality to enable discovery, reuse and citation and contain information about provenance and licensing. Their metadata are machine-actionable and standardized (e.g. Dublin Core, Data Cite, etc.) preferably using common non-proprietary formats and following the standards of the respective community the repository serves, where applicable
 - facilitate mid- and long-term preservation of the deposited material. They have mechanisms or provisions for expert curation and quality assurance for the accuracy and integrity of datasets and metadata, as well as procedures to liaise with depositors where issues are detected. They meet generally accepted international and national criteria for security to prevent unauthorized access and release of content and have different levels of security, depending on the sensitivity of the data being deposited, to maintain privacy and confidentiality.

Please note that some questions in this section are also pertinent to assess whether the repository metadata structure supports the provision of mandatory and recommended information related to the HE OS mandates. Metadata structure assessment is the objective of Section 4 of this survey.

* 3.1 Does the repository hold any type of certification?

- Yes
 No

* 3.2 Please select all certifications held by the repository

- Core Trust Seal
 Nestor Seal DIN31644
 ISO16363
 Other

3.3 You selected other as answer to the previous question. Please specify the certification(s) held by your repository

* 3.4 Please select all that apply

- the repository is disciplinary or domain specific - it accepts research outputs within a certain discipline or domain

- the repository is institutional - only researchers affiliated to a specific institution can deposit their research outputs in the repository
- the repository is general-purpose - it accepts research outputs from all disciplines or domains
- None of the above

* 3.5 None of the above was selected. Please use this space to describe your repository type

* 3.6 Is the repository recognised internationally?

- Yes
- No

* 3.7 Is the repository commonly used or endorsed by a specific research community?

The exact definition of what counts as endorsement by a research community cannot be precisely derived solely from the text provided in the HE AGA (page 155):

“...disciplinary and domain repositories commonly used and endorsed by the research communities. Such repositories should be recognised internationally.”

There is no single standardised system for organisations or individuals to codify and express commitment to and endorsement of specific repositories. For example, endorsement can be seen to happen through use, so that repositories popular among researchers from a specific research community can be considered endorsed by that research community.

- Yes
- No
- Not Sure

* 3.8 Please specify the research community that endorses your repository

* 3.9 Does the repository have a policy related to long-term preservation, content curation and security of uploaded materials?

- Yes
- No

* 3.10 Please provide the public link to the repository policy related to long-term preservation, content curation and security of uploaded materials

* 3.11 Are the repository metadata machine-actionable? *This question is also relevant for section 4.*

We refer to the definition of machine actionable metadata included in Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. Sci Data 3, 160018 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

- Yes
- No

* 3.12 Does the metadata schema of the repository refer to any specific standard (eg. Dublin Core, ISO 191**, etc.)? *This question is also relevant for section 4.*

- Yes
 No

* 3.13 Please provide the metadata standard used by your repository (e.g. Dublin Core, ISO 191**, etc.). *This question is also relevant for section 4.*

* 3.14 Is the repository able to assign persistent identifiers to uploaded items (e.g. digital object identifiers (DOIs), handles, access numbers, etc.)? *This question is also relevant for section 4.*

This question does not refer to the presence of a metadata field to mention the PID of a record, but rather to the **capacity of the repository to assign PIDs** to those digital objects that do not already have one.

- Yes
 No

* 3.15 Is there a dedicated field for license information in the metadata of uploaded items? *This question is also relevant for section 4.*

Can users assign a license to the records by filling in a dedicated metadata field?

- Yes
 No

4 Metadata structure to support compliance with Horizon Europe Open Science requirements

This section is designed to collect information on the metadata structure of the repository and its ability to support ERC Grantees' compliance with the Horizon Europe Open Science requirements.

The Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement and Annotated Model Grant Agreement state that:

Metadata of deposited **publications** must:

- provide information at least about the following:
 - publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue);
 - Horizon Europe or Euratom funding;
 - grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms;
 - persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant.
- Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

The required metadata listed above must be open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable).

Metadata of deposited **data** must:

- provide information at least about the following:
 - datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo);
 - Horizon Europe or Euratom funding;
 - grant project name, acronym and number;
 - licensing terms;
 - persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant.
- Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.

The required metadata listed above must be open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable).

4.1 The following table allows to provide information about the metadata fields that the repository offers for uploads. Please complete the table by ticking the corresponding cells:

Please note that the items in the table refer to the information that is available/retrievable for the deposited records, not necessarily metadata fields that are filled by authors at the time of the deposit. They could be captured by the repository from different sources.

	This information is captured by the repository	This information is not captured by the repository	The repository has a dedicated and separated metadata field for this item
* Description	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Author(s)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Title of the research output deposited	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Date of publication/deposit	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Venue of publication/deposit	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Embargo	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Grant project name	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Grant project acronym	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Grant project number	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* PID for the uploaded item (e.g. DOI)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
*			

PID(s) for the author(s) (ORCID, Researcher ID, SCOPUS ID, etc...)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* PID(s) for the author(s)' organisation/affiliation (eg. ROR ID)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Grant project PID(s) (eg. Grant DOI)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* Cross reference to other digital entities (i.e. information about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication or to re-use and validate the data)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
* PID(s) for cross referenced digital entities (i.e. PID of any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication or to re-use and validate the data)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

* 4.2 Does the repository allow researchers to indicate "Horizon Europe" in the metadata associated to the Funding or Grant?

- Yes, but **not** through a separated and dedicated metadata field
- Yes, through a separated and dedicated metadata field
- No
- Not sure/Cannot answer

* 4.3 Are the metadata of the repository open under a Creative Commons 0 (CC0) Public Domain Dedication or equivalent?

This refers to the license/copyright waiver assigned to the metadata that are identified in the AGA as required.

- Yes
- No

5 Additional information about the repository

* 5.1 Are you aware whether your repository is harvested by [OpenAIRE](#)?

You can search your repository via [OpenAIRE Explore](#)

- Yes, my repository is harvested by OpenAIRE
- No, my repository is not harvested by OpenAIRE
- Not yet/Not sure

* 5.2 Check all ERC panels that apply to the content that can be deposited in the repository. Please refer to [ERC panel structure 2024](#).

When selecting the panels, please think of the communities that produce results that can be deposited in your repository. Do not refer to panels that can reuse the contents of your repository. For example, satellite data can be produced by projects in panel PE10 and reused by projects in many different panels such as LS8, SH1 and SH7; in this case, only PE10 should be selected from the list. In case of a catch-all repository, please select "All ERC Panels below".

- All ERC Panels below**
- PE1 Mathematics
- PE2 Fundamental Constituents of Matter

- PE3 Condensed Matter Physics
- PE4 Physical and Analytical Chemical Sciences
- PE5 Synthetic Chemistry and Materials
- PE6 Computer Science and Informatics
- PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering
- PE8 Products and Processes Engineering
- PE9 Universe Sciences
- PE10 Earth System Science
- PE11 Materials Engineering
- LS1 Molecules of Life: Biological Mechanisms, Structures and Functions
- LS2 Integrative Biology: from Genes and Genomes to Systems
- LS3 Cellular, Developmental and Regenerative Biology
- LS4 Physiology in Health, Disease and Ageing
- LS5 Neuroscience and Disorders of the Nervous System
- LS6 Immunity, Infection and Immunotherapy
- LS7 Prevention, Diagnosis and Treatment of Human Diseases
- LS8 Environmental Biology, Ecology and Evolution
- LS9 Biotechnology and Biosystems Engineering
- SH1 Individuals, Markets and Organisations
- SH2 Institutions, Governance and Legal Systems
- SH3 The Social World and Its Diversity
- SH4 The Human Mind and Its Complexity
- SH5 Cultures and Cultural Production
- SH6 The Study of the Human Past
- SH7 Human Mobility, Environment, and Space
- SH8 Studies of Cultures and Arts

5.3 Please, use this space to provide us with links to some of the repository records. This would greatly facilitate the work of the expert in judging whether certain metadata criteria are fulfilled in a satisfactory way.

6 Comments and feedback

6.1 Was the repository included in the first version of the inventory of identified trusted repositories?

You can view the inventory in ANNEX 1 of the study at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7728016>

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

6.2 Did the published [study on the readiness of research data and literature repositories to facilitate compliance with the Open Science Horizon Europe MGA requirements](#) trigger any improvements or updates in your repository policies or structure?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

6.3 Feel free to use this space to include any comments and feedback for the survey purposes.